

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Measuring customers' buying attitude towards kitchenware products: A comparative study between domestic and foreign brands

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Abstract

This empirical study is conducted to investigate attributes that influence on attitude of customers towards domestic and foreign kitchenware brands in Bangladesh. The purpose of this study was to determine the key variables that influence customers' purchasing attitudes toward domestic and kitchenware brands, as well as to analyze the consequences of those aspects on their perceptions. For the study, a total five (5) attributes have been taken into account based on existing literature and field study. The study was carried out through a self-structured questionnaire which was distributed randomly and conveniently among the different customers and data were collected from 150 respondents for domestic kitchenware brands as well 150 respondents for foreign kitchenware brands; whereas collected 300 completed final questionnaires taken into account for the study's conclusion. The results of this investigation reveal that the attitudes of customers are almost the same in both domestic and foreign kitchenware brands. In both domestic and foreign kitchenware brands the quality, availability and after sales service attributes have direct favorable and positive influences on enhancing the customers buying attitude of the domestic and foreign kitchenware brands. Durability factors have negative influence on domestic kitchenware brands and price attributes has negative influence on foreign kitchenware brands. The findings of the investigation would assist the domestic and foreign kitchenware marketers to understand the customers buying attitude properly as well as to design an effective marketing strategy to sustain in the competitive market.

Keywords: Attributes; Customers; Kitchenware; Attitudes; Positive; Influence; Durability; Marketing; Strategy

1. Introduction

Customer buying attitude is stated as a feeling as favorable or unfavorable that customer has towards an object, Madhavan and Kaliyaperumal [1]. Customer buying behavior is defined by Dawson, Findlay and Sparks [2] as a collection of attitudes that describe patterns of customer choices. Customers are the focal point of any kinds of business activities. The study of consumer behavior is a broad field. Customers frequently make purchases, and a large number of them are ignorant about the factors that affect the specific products, services, or brands that they choose, Rani[3]. In the modern corporate environment, the client is a crucial component of every corporation that seeks to maximize profits. So, understanding the customer attitude regarding the companies' products and services are an extremely important for the kitchenware firms. There are many domestic and foreign brands are staying at the kitchenware market with the same market offers in Bangladesh. Both domestic and foreign kitchenware brands are producing all sorts of cooking utensils such as rice cooker, pressure cooker, gas stove, blinder and mixer and aluminium kettles which are used as household items. Local manufacturers are now steadily expanding their kitchenware line. About 35 Bangladeshi companies including Kiam, Nova, Hamko, RFL, Walton, KML and Sharif Melamine etc. have been

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manufacturing such cookware in their plants. In the last decade, they accounted for more than 70% of cookware sales in the country. On the other hand, there are many foreign kitchenware brands such as Prestige, Hawkins, Bajaj, Butterfly; Premier etc. are conducting their business activities along with the domestic kitchenware brands. As the metal products are essential consumer goods, so many are engaged in this business at present and an intensive competition in that business. The business landscape is now evolving quickly, and marketers are working hard to hold onto their places in this fiercely competitive sector. To remain in the market for an extended period of time, marketers must thereby understand the attitudes, preferences, emotions, tastes, and demands of their target audiences effectively. The kitchenware market is dominated by the domestic brand right now in Bangladesh. In this competitive market customer demand and wants are entirely different from each other, where many foreign kitchenware brands are offering almost the same kitchenware products along with domestic kitchenware brand in Bangladesh.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to measure customers' buying attitude towards kitchenware products in relation to domestic and foreign brands. The specific objectives are as follows:

- To determine the quality attributes that have influence on attitude of customers towards kitchenware product of domestic and foreign brands in Bangladesh.
- To measure the attitude of customers towards the domestic and foreign brands kitchenware products.
- To compare the customers' attitude on domestic brands as well as on foreign brands in Bangladesh based on selected common attributes.

Significance of the Study

An important factor in consumer behavior is attitude, which affects post-purchase assessments, brand loyalty, and buy decisions. Through comprehending the concept of attitude in customer behavior and the psychological processes that underlie it, companies can acquire significant insights into their intended market. All businesses must learn how to use innovation to seize opportunities, according to Ramli and Soelton[4]. This will help them address environmental issues while also demonstrating their commitment to supporting marketing for both domestic and international brands. The survey is crucial because it will paint a clear picture of consumers' attitudes toward kitchenware purchases and inform Bangladeshi producers and decision-makers about the volume, demand, and quality of their output. The producers can learn how to take on world's challenges.

Limitation of the Study

This study's scope is restricted to examining how consumers feel about purchasing kitchenware from Bangladesh and other countries. There are other quality factors that affect consumers' decisions when choosing domestic and international brands, but only five are included here.

1.1. Research Questions

- What are the quality-attributes that influence customers in selecting domestic and foreign brands kitchenware products?
- Does those variables significant or not on the customers' buying attitude of domestic and foreign brands kitchenware products?
- Are customers' attitude towards domestic and foreign brands of kitchenware products same in Bangladesh?

2. Reviews of Theories and Literatures

Numerous researches on consumers' perceptions of kitchenware products worldwide have been conducted. Although several studies have been conducted all over the world but unluckily in Bangladesh its very insignificant studies have been undertaken on the client sentiments about metal kitchenware products. A thorough analysis can be carried out because customers are the primary reason for buying kitchenware products. The customer is the most important component of consumer goods, as has always been claimed. It is important to observe the demands, attitudes, preferences, and beliefs of customers when they purchase metal kitchenware products in Bangladesh in order to gain insight into their purchasing behavior. In this circumstance, Fishbeins' Multi-Attribute Model[5] has been widely used by the marketers to understand consumer behavior in various aspects of developing effective marketing strategies. The model is based on some common attributes, Raheem[6]. According to the writer, the consumer buying attitude stimulated through the quality of packaging, color wrapper regarding the packaging, effective sales promotion tools and adequate service in relation to the kitchenware products are an extremely emergent factor for the success of any kinds

of metal industries. He defined packaging as the whole package which turn out an ultimate selling proposition that directly leads to impulse buying behavior of the customer. Also he argued in the study that attractive packaging and effective sales promotion tools increases sales and market share by reducing the cost in relation to the promotions and market that helps toward the company to catch the consumer attention and interest more effectively. Effective packaging draws a customer's attention to a particular brand, enhances its reputation, and influences the way the consumer feels about the product, Rundh [7]. In today's dynamic marketing communication landscape, packaging may be considered one of the most influential instruments, Anderson[8]. As such, a more thorough examination of its components and their influence on consumers' purchasing decisions is required. Attitudes reflect the customer positive or negative feelings toward executing a behavior. Ajzen[9] model showed that attitude on impression of behavioral intentions and also he suggests that purchase intentions embody not only psychological influences but also look on economic and environmental enumeration. Nasir and Adil [10] and Burns and Warren's [11]"Perceived quality" refers to the subjective assessment made by customers on the general excellence or superiority of a brand. In addition, consumer fulfillment is influenced by perceived performance and expectations, and it might result from perceived excellence, Chaudhuri[12]. The author Chavan [13], suggests a methodology that is Balanced Scorecard methodology which is a strategic performance management tool. Constructing a system for assessing performance was the primary aim of the balanced scorecard. Future driving factors was added by Balanced Scorecard on the basis of financial indicators. And examines innovation regarding business activities is the most prime issues in context of present competitive market. Businesses often focus their efforts on research and development particularly when it comes to innovation, seeking to create better goods and technologies. The intention to buy was shown to be positively correlated with emotional value and negatively correlated with perceived quality by Dee and Kim [14]. In accordance with Kojina et al [15], in "Multi attribute theory of attitude change", discussed some basic elements that are; price, quality, size, shape, design, durability, availability, packaging etc. which are used by the marketer to measure the attitudes and to change the attitudes. This model helps the marketers to change consumer's beliefs about brand's characteristics, to add new beliefs about a band. In this case, the marketers need to adopt segmentation and product development strategy should create a market profile. The perception of internal and extrinsic qualities-related characteristics is where the consumer's impression of quality originates, Gil[16]. Customer-driven quality has become a powerful strategic weapon for many businesses today, since it is a necessary component of their competitive strategy, Gobe[17]. As to Kumar and Kim[18] buyers could be inclined to purchase a certain brand due to their perception that it offers suitable characteristics, superior quality, or psychological benefits. According to Islam [19], the potentiality of renewable energy technologies (RETs) practicing in Bangladesh. Where by the customers will pay preference to use the cooking utensils which associated with renewable energy. The companies should move to the production in case of renewable energy for the customer preference, Madhavan and Kaliyaperuma [20]. Radha and Aithal [21] points out real or objectively quality, product-centered quality, and manufacturing excellence are all distinct from perceived quality. Some useful elements for customers' decision-making about green products are suggested by Rahnama and Rajabpour [22]. The study's dependent variable was option preference, while the independent factors were value to society, psychological value, conditional value, value in the context of epistemic potential, and value in relation to the environment. The most crucial elements in selecting environmentally friendly items are the independent variables, which include functional value-price, value in relation to the environment, and value in the event of epistemic discovery. Realizing the real customers of pure products, satisfying their needs, and finally adopting a practical action to protect and enhance the environment all of these were lacking in the items. To measure attitudes of customer Raufet et al [23] conducted another study on Akij Textile Limited in context of Bangladesh and he identified that the brand name, lower price and distributions reputations have a vital impact in selling Akij Textile products. Anilkumar and Joseph [24] presented a widely used, simple, and approved method for assessing attitudes. A point system is implemented, and customers are required to respond with roughly five points whenever a message is presented. Highly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, and highly agree are represented on this scale. The customer rates each point on the scale in relation to the statement. Afterwards these scales tested where high score represents positive attitudes and the lower score represents negative attitudes. Kumar and Kim [25] has been revealed that quality, price, environmental friendly and packaging has positively impact on consumer buying behavior of solar car in context of Indian subcontinent. Sharma et al [26] has identified some factors that can be affected at the time purchasing kitchenware products from domestic and foreign brands in the name of brand value, legitimate price, standard quality and after sales service and he also noticed that the success of metal industry is largely depends on post integration process, prompt responses and timely monitoring of market condition frequently. Watson [27] emphasizes the easy repair of the technological products. Customers will favor the products which are easy to be repaired. The products should have multiple times use capacity when it cracks up. Customer has a vital role in case of economic consideration about using technological products that affects the consumers' attitudes positive or negative.

2.1. Research Gap

This research will focus more on the empirical study based on field observations and the methodological study based on constructed variables like price, quality, availability, after-sale service, and durability. The results of several previous studies on customers' buying attitudes toward kitchenware products revealed that most of the research are analyzing more on the theoretical side that show the research gap. The customer's perspective and behavior with regard to the availability of kitchenware products will also be covered in greater detail in this study.

2.2. Conceptual Framework and Hypothesized Model

In this study, some variables have been used for the customers' buying attitudes to actual purchase in case of domestic and foreign kitchenware brands.

- Price
- Quality
- Availability
- After Sales Service
- Durability

Figure 1 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesized Model

Table 1 Hypotheses of the Study

Customer Buying Attitude (CBA)
Table No1 shows the consumer attitude which may be considered as a feeling of favourable or unfavourable that customer has towards objects. In this study the buying attitude of the customer for domestic and foreign kitchenware brand has measured with the help of five factors in the name of price, quality, availability, after sales service and durability.
Price(P)

<p>Price is the sum of money that is required to purchase any good or service, Kotler and Armstrong[28]. Generally, all elements of marketing mix generate cost expect price and price generate revenues to cover cost. According to Satit, Tat, Rasli, Chin and Sukati [29] declared that among the product, price, place and promotion is the most influential factor that affect consumers' purchasing decision in most cases. Munusamy and Hoo [30] stated that pricing strategy has an immense impact on customers' intention to buy. That's why following hypothesis was developed-</p>	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
H1: Perceived price of domestic kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.	H1: Perceived price of foreign kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.
<p>Quality(Q)</p> <p>Quality can be defined as zero defects. Quality also known to us the ability of a product to fulfil the customer expectation. Quality is the key factor to purchase the Kitchenware products for a customer who is addressed by Sweeney and Soutar [31]. They think Kitchenware products in the light of domestic and foreign brand has a great impact in customer buying attitude. So, H2 was proposed.</p>	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
H2: Quality of domestic kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.	H2: Quality of foreign kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.
<p>Availability(A)</p> <p>Kitchenware products are available in the context of Bangladesh for all the time and the customer can purchase their products all the year round without any hesitation. So, H3 was proposed.</p>	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
H3: Availability of domestic kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.	H3: Availability of foreign kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.
<p>After Sales Service(ASS)</p> <p>After sales service means to support or services that a company or businesses provides to its customers after they buy a product or services from a company or businesses. It might include advice on how to use a product or service, onboarding guides, providing responsive and good customer service, training on products, listening and providing efficient customer feedback, refunds and exchanges etc. In recent time, businesses are paying more attention towards customers after sales services. Providing great after sales services improves customer retention and increases the likelihood of customers purchasing from a company again and again. So, H4 was proposed.</p>	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
H4: After sales service of domestic kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.	H4: After sales service of foreign kitchenware brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.
<p>Durability(D)</p> <p>Durability is the ability of a physical product to resist normal use's demands for the duration of its intended lifespan without requiring major maintenance or repair, Holbrook [32]. The definition of durability, according to Webster's Dictionary, is the capacity to continue continuously or for a prolonged period of time under any circumstances; the ability to withstand agents or effects that have the tendency to induce alterations, deterioration, or disintegration; and the state or characteristic of being durable. Products and services durability in prospects of kitchenware markets has a great impact on customer buying attitude because customers are naturally prone to much more durable kitchenware products and services.</p>	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
H5: Durability of kitchenware products in terms of domestic brand has negatively affected the customer buying attitude.	H5: Durability of kitchenware products in terms of foreign brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude.

3. Methodology

Methodology indicate that the procedure of undertaking research. The business research report has been conducted in a very systematic procedure starting from selection of the topics to the final report preparation. This study examined consumer attitudes regarding domestic and imported kitchenware, as well as their levels of satisfaction and dissatisfaction with the suggested brands. A self-structured questionnaire with five criteria—strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree—was used to gather primary data.

3.1. Nature of the Study

Descriptive (Quantitative) research has been used for the study.

3.2. Sources of Data

For this study both primary and secondary data have been used. Between primary and secondary sources, the majority of the information was gathered from primary sources. To collect the primary data self-structured questionnaire and direct observations have been used. For collecting secondary data, the different journals, books, related publications and websites have been used.

3.3. Methods of Data Collection

For data collection self-structured questionnaire has been used and data has been gathered from the different customers of domestic and foreign kitchenware products.

3.4. Scaling Techniques

The degree of agreement or disagreement with each of a sequence of assertions was indicated by the five response categories on the Likert scale (Non-comparative Scaling Technique): 1- Strongly agree, 2- Agree, 3- Neither agree nor disagree, 4- Disagree, 5- Strongly disagree.

3.5. Sampling Design and Techniques

3.5.1. Target Population

For this study the target population was all of the customers of domestic and foreign kitchenware brands in Bangladesh.

3.5.2. Sampling Technique

Simple random and convenience sampling method has been taken for selecting samples.

3.5.3. Sample Size

Total Sample size was 300 whereas 150 for domestic kitchenware brands and the rest 150 for foreign kitchenware brands. Data has been collected from 150 respondents of both domestic and foreign kitchenware brands.

3.5.4. Data Analysis Technique

MS Excel and the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS version 21) are used to evaluate the data for this study.

4. Result

4.1. From Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Table No. 2 illustrates the respondents' demographic profile. The demographic profile of the respondents depicts that the majority of the participants were male (66.7%) and female (33.3%); among them, most are 20–25 years old (45.3%) and 26–30 years old (36.7%) and have completed graduation (45.3%) and (36.7%) subsequently. Among the 150 respondents, income of 81 respondents was below 10000, 38 were 10,000-20,000, 27 were 20,000-30,000 and 4 were above 40,000. Additionally, among the respondents, 59 were students, 26 were businessmen, 14 had private jobs, 6 had government. jobs, and 45 were others, respectively.

Table 2 Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Variables	Categories	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	100	66.7%
	Female	50	33.3%
Marital Status	Married	28	18.7%
	Unmarried	122	81.3%
Age	Below 20 years	9	6%
	20-25 years	68	45.3%
	26-30 years	55	36.7%
	31-35 years	16	10.7%
	36-40 years and above	2	1.3%
Education Level	SSC (Secondary School Certificate)	16	10.7%
	HSC (Higher Secondary Certificate)	18	12%
	Graduation	73	48.7%
	Masters/Post-graduation	38	25.3%
	Others	5	3.3%
Occupation	Student	59	39.3%
	Business	26	17.3%
	Private Job	14	9.3%
	Govt. Job	6	4%
	Others	45	30%
Income Level	Below 10,000	81	54%
	10,000 to 20,000	38	25.3%
	20,000 to 30,0000	27	18%
	30,000 to 40,000 and Above	4	2.7%

Source: Researcher's own collection and through the use of Excel Sheet-2010.

4.2. From Elementary Data

Furthermore, the respondents to this survey provided some basic information regarding their purchasing attitudes, which is shown in table 02 below:

Table 3 Basic Information about customer buying attitude of the respondents

Variables	Categories	Domestic		Foreign	
		Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
Do you know about Kitchenware Product?	Yes	150	100%	150	100%
	No	--	--	--	--
Have you purchased any Kitchenware product?	Yes	150	100%	150	100%
	No	--	--	--	--
	Domestic	150	100%	--	--

What types of Kitchenware product have you purchased?	Foreign	--	--	150	100%	
Which brand products have you purchased? (In case of domestic brand)	Domestic	Kiam	64	42.7%	--	--
		Nova	46	30.7%	--	--
		Hamko	18	12%	--	--
		RFL	5	2.7%	--	--
		Walton	8	5.35%	--	--
		Sharif Melamine	4	2.7%	--	--
		Singer	5	3.35%	--	--
	Foreign	Prestige	--	--	76	50.7%
		Hawkins	--	--	42	28%
		Bajaj	--	--	6	4%
		Butterfly	--	--	18	12%
Premier		--	--	8	5.3%	
Reasons for purchasing?	Reasonable Price	91	60.7%	--	--	
	High Quality	8	5.3%	86	57.3%	
	Availability	23	15.3%	23	15.3%	
	After Sales Service	28	18.7%	--	--	
	Durability	--	--	41	27.3%	
Most frequently purchase category:	Rice Cooker	80	53.3%	65	43.3%	
	Pressure Cooker	17	11.3%	19	12.7%	
	Gas Stove	8	5.3%	20	13.3%	
	Blender and Mixer	6	4%	12	8%	
	Others	--	--	34	22.7%	
Information about Kitchenware product	By Family/friends	61	40.7%	72	48%	
	Direct Mail	14	9.3%	9	6%	
	Press Advertisement	26	17.3%	30	20%	
	Reference Website	2	1.3%	10	6.7%	
	Social Media	7	4.7%	19	12.7%	
	TV Advertisement	39	26%	10	6.7%	
Preference for quality while buying Kitchenware products	Intermediaries	72	48%	71	47.3%	
	Standard	52	35%	40	26.7%	
	Latest /Advanced	26	17%	39	26%	
Frequency of purchasing Kitchenware products	Frequently	--	--	--	--	
	Weekly	--	--	--	--	
	Monthly	17	11.3%	11	7.3%	

	When Needed	133	88.7%	139	92.7%
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Source: Researcher's own collection and through the use of Excel Sheet-2010.

Table No. 03 demonstrate the respondents' basic information in the light of domestic and foreign kitchenware brands. In the case of domestic kitchenware brands, 100% of respondents were known, and all were purchased from domestic kitchenware brands. Kiam and Sharif melamine brands were the most popular among respondents, accounting for 42.7% and 2.7% of purchases, respectively. Rice cookers were purchased by 53.3% of respondents, pressure cookers by 11.3%, gas stoves by 5.3%, and blenders and mixers by 4%. Among the 150 respondents, 61 got information from family or friends, 14 from direct mail, 26 from press advertisements, 2 from reference websites, 7 from social media, and 39 from TV advertisements subsequently. The maximum number of customers (60.7%) bought domestic kitchenware products for a reasonable price. Moreover, of the people who involved in this study, 52% had a had a preference for standards-quality products, 26% for the latest and most advanced and 72% were for intermediaries. In this survey, 11.3% of participants said they would like to buy on a monthly basis, and the rest, 88.7%, commented that they would only buy when necessary.

In the case of foreign kitchenware brands, 100% of respondents were known, and all were purchased from foreign kitchenware brands. The highest and lowest number of respondents purchased from Prestige and Bajaj brands, with 50.7% and 4%, respectively. Rice cookers were purchased by 43.3% of respondents, pressure cookers by 12.7%, gas stoves by 13.3%, blenders and mixers by 8%, and others by 22.7%. Among the 150 respondents, 72 got information from family or friends, 9 from direct mail, 30 from press advertisements, 10 from reference websites, 19 from social media, and 10 from TV advertisements subsequently. The maximum number of customers (57.3%) bought foreign kitchenware products of its high quality. Moreover, of the people who participated in this study, 26.7% preferred standards-quality products, 26% preferred the latest or advanced, and 47.3% preferred intermediaries. In this survey, 7.3% of participants said they would like to buy on a monthly basis, and the rest, 92.7%, commented that they would only buy when necessary.

4.3. From Variable Analysis

4.3.1. Reliability Analysis for Domestic and Foreign Brand

Table 4 Reliability Analysis

Domestic Kitchenware Brand		Foreign Kitchenware Brand	
Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items	Cronbach's Alpha	Number of Items
0.910	21	0.872	21

Source: Researcher's own collection and through the use of SPSS version, 2014.

In case of domestic brand, Cornbach's Alpha is tasted for the study of 21 items and overall reliability for the measure was 0.910 which is matched with the standard value 0.60 (Nunnally and Bernstein[33] and it is indicate that above 0.60 value of reliability is an acceptable level of reliability. So the questionnaire used was reliable for information collection.

On the contrary, for foreign brand, Cornbach's Alpha is tasted for the study of 21 items and overall reliability for the measure was 0.872 which is matched with the standard value 0.60 (Nunnally and Bernstein[34] and it is indicate that above 0.60 value of reliability is an acceptable level of reliability. So the questionnaire used was reliable for information collection.

4.3.2. KMO (KAISER-MEYER-OLKIN)

Table No 04 shows the sample adequacy test which was conducted to the features of the consumer buying attitude in order to ascertain whether the sample was adequate to take into account the data, that is, whether the data was normally distributed or not. Regarding domestic kitchenware brands, the KMO value of.811 indicates that the sample size was sufficient to regard the data as normally distributed, since a KMO value of 0.70 or higher indicates that the data is deemed normal. Conversely, for international cookware brands, the KMO value of 0.766 indicates that the sample size was adequate to account for the normally distributed data, since a KMO value of 0.70 or more is considered to indicate that the data is normally distributed.

Table 5 KMO and Bartlett's Test

KMO and Bartlett's Test					
Domestic Brand			Foreign Brand		
Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.811	Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		0.766
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2819.947	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	2544.320
	df	210		df	210
	Sig.	0.000		Sig.	0.000

Source: Researcher's own collection and through the use of SPSS version, 2014.

4.3.3. Hypotheses Testing

In hypothesis testing, a structural model is used to help researchers making decisions about the offered hypotheses. It also assists in understanding the link between the dependent and independent variables. Structural equation modeling is used to test various hypothesized causal relationship among the customer buying attitude towards kitchenware products of domestic and foreign kitchenware brands in Bangladesh.

Dependent Variable: Customer Buying Attitude

Table 6 Multiple Regression Analysis

	Hypothesis	Independent Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	P	Decision
			Beta	Std. Error	Beta			
Domestic Kitchenware Brands		(Constant)	0.790	0.194		4.073	0.000	
	H1	Price	0.174	0.041	0.152	4.284	0.000	Supported
	H2	Quality	0.340	0.049	0.488	6.898	0.000	Supported
	H3	Availability	0.215	0.057	0.263	3.798	0.000	Supported
	H4	After Sales Service	0.175	0.080	0.127	2.191	0.030	Supported
	H5	Durability	-0.063	0.040	-0.048	-1.551	0.123	Unsupported
Foreign Kitchenware Brands		(Constant)	2.616	0.206		12.679	0.000	
	H1	Price	-0.080	0.085	-0.074	-0.936	0.351	Unsupported
	H2	Quality	0.185	0.044	0.180	4.197	0.000	Supported
	H3	Availability	0.303	0.052	0.553	5.819	0.000	Supported
	H4	After Sales Service	0.464	0.108	0.722	4.292	0.000	Supported
	H5	Durability	0.286	0.122	0.358	2.345	0.020	Supported

Source: Researcher's own collection and through the use of SPSS version, 2014. [Note: H= Hypothesis, Std. Error= Standard Error, T= Hypothesis Test Statistic, P=Probability]

In case of domestic kitchenware brands,

The multiple regression analysis model exhibits that price of kitchenware products has positive influence on enhancing customer buying attitude ($\beta = 0.174$, $P = 0.000$). Tables 04 also shows that quality ($\beta = 0.340$, $P = .000$), availability ($\beta = 0.215$, $P = 0.000$), after sales service ($\beta = 0.175$, $P = 0.030$) of kitchenware products have positive impact on enhancing the buying attitude of customers towards domestic brands. On the other hand, durability ($\beta = -0.063$, $P = 0.123$) of kitchenware products has negative influence on customer buying attitude.

On the other hand, for foreign kitchenware brands,

The multiple regression analysis model exhibits that quality of kitchenware products has positive influence on enhancing customer buying attitude ($\beta = 0.185$, $P = 0.000$). Tables 05 also shows that availability ($\beta = 0.303$, $P = .000$), after sales service ($\beta = 0.464$, $P = 0.000$), durability ($\beta = 0.286$, $P = 0.020$) of kitchenware products have positive impact on enhancing the buying attitude of customers towards domestic brands. On the other hand, price ($\beta = -.080$, $P = 0.351$) of kitchenware products has negative influence on customer buying attitude.

5. Discussions

Findings of the study reveal that the attitudes of customers are almost the same in both domestic and foreign kitchenware brand. In both domestic and foreign kitchenware brand hypotheses H_2 , H_3 and H_4 in terms of quality, availability and after sales service are accepted indicating that there are no significant differences between the customers' attitude towards kitchenware products in both domestic and foreign brand. It means the quality, availability and after sales service attributes has direct strong influence on enhancing the consumer buying intention in case of domestic and foreign kitchenware brand. However, the study revealed that in other 2 attributes namely price and durability; the customers are not the same in both domestic and foreign kitchenware brand. There are significant differences in the price and durability attributes. In case of domestic brands, the durability attributes are rejected. Durability has negative impact on enhancing the customers' buying attitude ($\beta = -0.063$, $P = 0.123$) for domestic kitchenware brands. It represents the customers' think that domestic kitchenware brands are not durable in comparison with foreign kitchenware brands that result in customers' buying attitude are negatively affected in selecting foreign kitchenware brands. On the contrary, for foreign kitchenware brands the price attributes ($\beta = -0.080$, $P = 0.351$) are rejected indicating that customers have negative impact on buying attitude in choosing foreign kitchenware brands. It suggests the customers' think that foreign kitchenware brands are high price in comparison with domestic kitchenware brands.

Recommendations

Table 7 Some recommendations for domestic and foreign kitchenware brands

Price	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
Domestic kitchenware marketer can retain the price level to enhance the sales of kitchenware products.	Foreign kitchenware marketer should change the price structure or they can adjust or set the price structure in accordance with the domestic kitchenware brand to keep peace with the present competitive market.
Quality	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
Domestic kitchenware marketer should pay more attention towards the quality of kitchenware products to sustain the marketer for a long time.	According to the findings, mostly customers take or buy foreign kitchenware band owing to high level of quality. So foreign marketer should retain the quality level of their kitchenware products.
Availability	
The findings indicate that the availability of domestic kitchenware products has positive impact on customer buying attitude. The domestic kitchenware marketer can take different types of promotional strategy in more to make available the product. As a result, customer buying attitude will be increased.	According to the findings, the foreign kitchenware brand is available in urban areas but it is not available in rural areas as like domestic kitchenware brand. So they can take promotion and distribution strategy to make available the products in the rural areas that will lead to increase the customer buying attitude.
After Sales Service	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
According to the findings, after sales service attributes has positive impact on customer buying attitude in selecting domestic kitchenware band.	Providing great after sales service improves customer retention and an increase the likelihood of customer purchasing from a brand again and again. So foreign

So, the marketer of domestic kitchenware band can provide the adequate level of after sales service to the customers to satisfy the customer in more that results in high customer retention rate. As a result, customer buying attitude will be increased.	kitchenware marketer can increase after sales service according to per customers.
Durability	
Domestic Kitchenware Brands	Foreign Kitchenware Brands
The findings of this study are revealed that the durability attributes have negative impact on customer buying attitude. It means the customer of domestic kitchenware brand thinks that domestic kitchenware products are less durable than foreign kitchenware products. So, the marketer of domestic kitchenware bands should pay more attention on durability so that customer can get strong confident in selecting domestic kitchenware brand.	According to the findings, durability of kitchenware products in terms of foreign brand has positively affected the customer buying attitude. So the marketer of foreign kitchenware brand can retain the level of durability to enhance the sales. Durability of a product would increase the confidence level of savvy customer.

6. Conclusion and Future Research Directions

Almost all of the variables, including as quality, availability, and after-sales service, are the same in both domestic and international kitchenware bands, according to the statistical data analysis and findings. Furthermore, certain attributes—like durability and price—differ from one another. both native and international brands of kitchenware. This indicates that while price and durability have a negative influence on the customer's buying attitude, quality, availability, and after-sale service have a positive impact. The research can assist both domestic and international kitchenware manufacturers in customizing their marketing strategies, enhancing user experience, analyzing competitors, and making well-informed judgments regarding regional expansion by identifying the elements that influence purchase intention. The results of this study will be useful in determining the requirements and preferences of consumers who wish to buy kitchenware from both domestic and international brands. These results can be used by marketers of both domestic and overseas kitchenware brands to create an efficient marketing plan and meet consumer expectations. Overseas and domestic marketers must leave a lasting impression on consumers in order to survive in the cutthroat industry. Domestic kitchenware brands are up against fierce competition from these overseas names. As a result, the study's findings may help domestic and international kitchenware marketers properly grasp their target market and create a winning marketing plan to compete in it. The study did, however, have certain shortcomings. This study was limited in scope (it only included 150 respondents for domestic kitchenware brands and 150 respondents for foreign kitchenware brands) and restricted in geography (it only included the Bangladeshi districts of Kushtia and Jhenaidah). Even though the study only looks at a small number of variables, certain other factors might have an impact on the buying intentions of the public. Therefore, more study might be done in Bangladesh using a larger sample size and in different regions to find more factors that influence consumers' purchasing attitudes toward local and international kitchenware brands.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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